

Supporting Information for the article:

Differential effects of FXR or TGR5 activation in cholangiocarcinoma progression

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Materials and Methods

Human samples. Supplementary table 1 shows the clinical information of patients included in the analysis of *FXR* or *TGR5*.

Gene expression by qRT-PCR. Supplementary Table 2 shows the primers employed for quantitative polymerase chain reaction (qRT-PCR).

Mitochondrial energetic metabolism. Oxygen consumption rate (OCR) was measured in an XF96 Extracellular Flux Analyzer (Seahorse Bioscience) using the *XF Cell Mito Stress Test Kit* and metabolic parameters were calculated as indicated by Seahorse Bioscience and as described in Supplementary figure 1.

Supplementary figure 1. Functional evaluation of the mitochondrial energetic metabolism. Oxygen consumption rate (OCR) *in situ* measurement during treatment with different mitochondrial inhibitors. Adapted from Seahorse Bioscience.

Supplementary table 1. Clinical information of the San Sebastian cohort of patients for *FXR* and *TGR5* expression analysis

	Gender	Age		Disease	
		Average	Standard Deviation	iCCA	eCCA
FXR	Male	68,90	9,09	7	3
	Female	67,75	15,84	3	1
TGR5	Male	62,00	9,23	7	1
	Female	64,86	14,19	4	3

Abbreviations: iCCA, intrahepatic CCA; eCCA, extrahepatic CCA.

Supplementary table 2. Primers sequences used for qRT-PCR of human mRNAs

Primers	Sequences
<i>FXR</i>	<i>Forward</i> 5'-ACAGAACAAGTGGCAGGTC-3' <i>Reverse</i> 5'-CTGAAGAAACCTTTACACCCCTC-3'
<i>TGR5</i>	<i>Forward</i> 5'-TTGGTCCACTTGTGCTCTTC-3' <i>Reverse</i> 5'-GCTGGTGTGTAGTGGTCTTC-3'
<i>Ki67</i>	<i>Forward</i> 5'-CCACGCAAACCTCTCCTTGTA-3' <i>Reverse</i> 5'-TTGTCAACTGCGGTTGCTCC-3'
<i>PCNA</i>	<i>Forward</i> 5'-ACACTAAGGGCCGAAGATAACG-3' <i>Reverse</i> 5'-ACAGCATCTCCAATATGGCTGA-3'
<i>Cyclin D1</i>	<i>Forward</i> 5'-GCTGCGAAGTGGAACCATC-3' <i>Reverse</i> 5'-CCTCCTTCTGCACACATTTGAA-3'
<i>Cyclin D3</i>	<i>Forward</i> 5'-TACCCGCCATCCATGATCG-3' <i>Reverse</i> 5'-AGGCAGTCCACTTCAGTGC-3'
<i>Cdc25A</i>	<i>Forward</i> 5'-CTGCCTGCACTCTCATGGAC-3' <i>Reverse</i> 5'-CTGTCCAGAGGCTTGCCATG-3'
<i>GAPDH</i>	<i>Forward</i> 5'-CCAAGGTCATCCATGACAAC-3' <i>Reverse</i> 5'-TGTCATACCAGGAAATGAGC-3'

Results

Role of FXR or TGR5 activation on the expression of proliferation markers within the tumors of an orthotopic mouse model of CCA. The effect of FXR or TGR5 activation (with OCA or INT-777, respectively) was evaluated on the *in vivo* CCA tumor growth by measuring the mRNA expression of proliferation markers. A decreasing trend is observed in *Cdc25a*, *Cyclin D1* and *Cyclin D3* expression in the OCA treated group (Supplementary figure 2).

Supplementary figure 2. Effects of OCA and INT-777 in liver xenograft tumoral expression of proliferation markers. mRNA expression levels of proliferation (i.e. *Cdc25a*, *cyclin D1* and *cyclin D3*) markers in liver orthotopic CCA tumors.

Effect of FXR activation with OCA on TFK1 CCA cell proliferation and survival. OCA treatment also inhibits the proliferation of TFK1 cells, another CCA cell line, in a dose-dependent manner (Supplementary figure 3), without inducing cell death, unless toxic at the highest dose (50 μ M) (Supplementary figure 4).

Supplementary figure 3. The FXR agonist OCA inhibits TFK1 CCA cell proliferation in a dose-dependent manner. Flow cytometry-based proliferation (by CFSE) of CCA cells (i.e. TFK1) under increasing doses of OCA for 48h compared to non-treated control cells.

Supplementary figure 4. The FXR agonist OCA does not affect TFK1 CCA cell viability at 25 μM. Flow cytometry-based apoptosis assays by Annexin V and Propidium Iodide staining in CCA cells (i.e. TFK1) non-treated or treated with increasing doses of OCA. Representative histograms and corresponding quantification.